

InvestCEC

Summary of support and facilitation measures and activities mid-project

MATERALIA

Funded by
the European Union

Project information

Project name	InvestCEC
Full project name	Supporting the transition towards circular economy in European cities and regions: Development of a replicable model for local circular economy projects
Grant number	101082131
Project coordinator	
Project duration	01/11/2022 – 31/10/2025

Document information

Deliverable name and number	Support and facilitation measures and activities mid-project		
Due date	April 2024		
Actual submission date			
Contributing partners	ALL		
Deliverable type			
R	Document, report		R
DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype		
DEC	Websites, patent filings, videos etc.		
OTHER			
Dissemination level			
PU	Public		
SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement		

Version	Date	Author	Comments
1	04/24	Joseph HURTADO	First version from this deliverable

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1. Introduction and Background

1.1. Executive Summary

This deliverable provides an in-depth look at the mid-project support and facilitation measures undertaken to advance the InvestCEC project. These activities are essential as they lay the groundwork for achieving the project's overarching goal of developing a replicable model for implementing circular economy projects in European cities and regions. The InvestCEC project continues to leverage the city of Klagenfurt as a test bed to demonstrate the viability and replicability of the model. Key activities include stakeholder engagement and extensive dissemination efforts aimed at spreading knowledge about the benefits and practices of the circular economy.

Significant milestones highlighted in the deliverable include the successful execution of knowledge, confidence, and capacity-building measures such as participation in major circular economy forums and events, proactive engagement in strategic events across Europe, the establishment of a resource page, the release of informative newsletters, professional articles, the launch of a call for entrepreneurs, and the first InvestCEC circular economy day in Klagenfurt.

This deliverable also outlines our future and trajectory in terms of thematic webinars, marketplace development, financial opportunities, and the preparation for a second call for entrepreneurs.

1.2. Methodology

This deliverable revolves around a collaborative approach that leverages the strengths and expertise of all partners involved in the project. This section outlines the various methods and strategies implemented to gather comprehensive evidence of the activities undertaken the last year, which have contributed to engaging with stakeholders, disseminating activities and results, and strengthening our connections with our funding initiative, the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI).

1. Collaboration and Communication:

To ensure effective collaboration and communication among all partners, the project employed several strategies:

1. **Regular Project Meetings:** Scheduled meetings provided a structured platform for partners to discuss and evaluate the progress of the project. These meetings served for planning, addressing challenges, and making strategic decisions, ensuring that all partners were aligned with the project vision.
2. **Bi-lateral Calls:** To complement the larger project meetings, bi-lateral calls were conducted between individual partners. These calls allowed for more detailed discussions to address specific issues, facilitating more targeted and efficient problem-solving.
3. **Internal Documentation:** Partners created also internal documents that recorded the outcomes and insights of some specific activities within the project. This documentation was shared in order to help partners stay awarded of project advancements and upcoming activities such as webinars and events to be attended.

2. Data Collection and Analysis

To systematically collect and analyse data related to the project activities, the following methods were utilised:

1. **Surveys:** Surveys were undertaken to gather qualitative and quantitative data directly from stakeholders and participants involved in or affected by the project activities.
2. **Activity Reports:** Partners submitted often communicated summaries on some activities undertaken, including objectives, processes, outcomes, and stakeholder feedback. These reports were crucial for assessing the success of each activity and understanding its contribution to the project's overall goals.
3. **Review and Integration:** The collected data and insights from all partners were regularly reviewed and integrated during project meetings. This integration process helped identify best practices, lessons learned, and areas needing improvement, which were then documented in this final deliverable.

2. Knowledge, Confidence and Capacity building: Activities and Facilitation Measures

It marks 4 years since the launch of the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI), a European Commission initiative launched by the Directorate-General for Research and Innovation as part of the EU Circular Economy Action Plan 2020. Since then, this initiative has contributed vastly to policy objectives dealing with sustainable growth and reducing the environmental footprint of economic activities within the EU, specifically aligning with the goals of the EU Green Deal and the EU Bioeconomy Strategy.

From its genesis back in 2020, the CCRI has been actively involved, not only in creating a community designed to foster collaboration and knowledge sharing among a wide range of stakeholders coming across the quadruple helix, (cities, regions, industry representatives, research and technology organisations, and civil society), but also supporting the funding and uptake of a diverse range of projects aimed at embedding and expanding the principles of circular economy, transforming it into a mainstream and widely adopted practice throughout Europe's cities and regions.

Funding has been allocated to initiatives such as InvestCEC, which are designed to facilitate the shift towards a circular economy within European cities and regions by creating a model that uses the city of Klagenfurt as a test bed; the latter, being a pioneer, should produce results with a high potential of replicability across different EU cities and regions. To do so, InvestCEC is committed to foster replication by providing valuable information and resources to a broad audience, cities, local and regional governments, general stakeholders, and individuals interested in sustainable development and circular economy practices. In this manner, content materials, documentation, and activities undertaken by the project that can be used for replication will be openly accessible through the project's website and additional platforms (e.g., Horizon results platform, through CCRI and its coordination services, additional relevant repositories and the Zenodo community).

2.1. Resource page

Resources and materials to be utilised by stakeholders interested in getting acquainted with InvestCEC's activities advancements, as well as other related documentation should be able to find in our resources section. The communications manager (Greenovate Europe) and the Replication manager (Materalialia) have strategically dedicated these sections to the publication of:

- **Data management plan – D1.2**

The data management plan outlines the main elements of the data management that will be used by the InvestCEC Consortium regarding the project data. It includes descriptions of the way that data is handled during and after the project, the type of data to be collected, processed, or generated, the methodology and standards to be applied to ensure that the data management meets the FAIR data principle and whether and how the data will be shared.

- **Detailed online platform functional and technical specifications – D2.2**

This deliverable aims to provide the technical specifications for the InvestCEC stakeholder platform, which will serve as a meeting point for stakeholders involved in each local/regional circular economy project where they can update, exchange information, and monitor project progress. However, based on the decisions made at the last consortium meeting in Valladolid, Spain, it was collectively agreed to abandon the development of a standalone platform. The reason for that was two-fold: a. this platform was designed and developed following a traditional online forum that was extensively used in the past, but in contemporary life this method is no longer as inviting and/or engaging as modern social networks discussion means, and in line with that; b. the actual engagement of stakeholders was non-existent. Therefore, we have decided to abandon this platform and instead, its functionality will be integrated into other existing communication methods, which are already proven to be engaging relevant traffic. This includes the project website, where stakeholders can make enquiries about replication, follow project updates through professional articles, or directly access our newsletter. Furthermore, the consortium has decided to initiate discussions on LinkedIn due to its greater proven outreach potential. The demonstration of the InvestCEC model will continue in the City of Klagenfurt, Austria, adapting these new strategies for stakeholder engagement.

- **Circular economy investments-Financial barriers and potential measures to address them – D3.2.**

This deliverable focuses on identifying and providing measures to address the main financial obstacles and challenges that hinder or slow down the transition to the circular economy in cities and regions, such as unclear business models, lack of profitable business cases, coordination of public and private funders/investors, risk assessment and management, accounting for non-monetary co-benefits in financial models, and assessment and management of non-monetary risks in financial models.

- **Replication plan – D3.1**

The initial replication plan presented on the resource page outlines general guidelines for adapting and replicating the InvestCEC model in various cities and regions. It will undergo a second round of evaluation, revision, and enrichment, incorporating valuable feedback and insights from project partners and first-hand experiences gained during implementation.

- **Plan for dissemination and exploitation – including communication activities – D4.2**

This deliverable aims to explain the InvestCEC communication, dissemination, and exploitation strategy, which will help maximise the impact of the project. The plan is objective oriented, and explains the activities planned during the project duration.

Furthermore, in the resources section, the InvestCEC website has dedicated a section in which press communication for the Calls for entrepreneurs has been published in English and local languages (German) as well as tools outlining the InvestCEC project flyer and the project's visual identity.

2.2. Spreading the word: Engaging Events and informative webinars

Here is a detailed summary of the events that have taken place over the course of 2024 up to April 2024:

- **Keynote InvestCEC – Carinthian Waste Management Associations, held on the 8th of January 2024 – STW.**

Gernot Bogensberger, Head of the Waste Management Department for the city of Klagenfurt, presented the InvestCEC project at the regional waste management association meeting held in Carinthia in early 2024. He represented the city of Klagenfurt and took this opportunity to introduce the project. His presentation played a crucial role in disseminating information and fostering collaborative discussions among various stakeholders. These stakeholders, who are keen on promoting sustainable waste management practices, engaged actively in exploring how the InvestCEC initiatives could be implemented locally to enhance environmental sustainability in Carinthia.

- **World Circular Economy Forum – Brussels, Belgium, held on the 15 to 18 April – Greenovate! Europe**

Greenovate! Europe, representing the InvestCEC project, participated in the World Circular Economy Forum (WCEF) which focused on how various global regions are employing circular solutions to address challenges. The event attracted stakeholders from over 100 countries, providing an excellent platform for networking. This was a valuable opportunity for Greenovate! Europe to engage with other Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI) projects and stakeholders, particularly with DEFINITE-CCRI and CircularInvest, enhancing connections within the Circular Investment Readiness Network.

- **Circular economy day 2024 – Klagenfurt, Austria, held the 18th of April 2024 – organised by STW Klagenfurt, Venionaire**

The Circular Economy Day 2024, was organised by Stadtwerke Klagenfurt and Venionaire Capital as part of InvestCEC and gathered over 30 participants at the Lakeside Science & Technology Park. Two top startups from the InvestCEC Pitch Competition were granted the opportunity to qualify for a live pitch session in front of the jury. Following a rigorous selection process, AES Autonomous Energy Systems (DE) and Sustario (AT) were selected to present their innovative ideas to Erwin Smole and Nadja Sussitz (both from Stadtwerke Klagenfurt), Berthold Baurek-Karlic (Venionaire Capital), Alexander Mann (StartupCarinthia), and Gernot Bogensberger (Magistrat Klagenfurt), with the aim of receiving valuable feedback. In the end, Marco Karber and Andres Sheldrick from AES Autonomous Energy Systems GmbH in Germany won with their method that turns leftover plastic into useful oil.

The primary objective of the Circular Economy Day 2024 was to foster collaboration and innovation in the field of sustainable practices. By providing a platform for startups to present their ideas and receive feedback from industry experts, the event aimed to encourage the development of innovative solutions that promote circular economy.

The event successfully highlighted the importance of collaboration between various stakeholders in advancing sustainable practices. It showcased innovative solutions from startups like AES Autonomous Energy Systems, demonstrating the potential for transformative change in addressing environmental challenges. Additionally, the recognition of innovative ideas and the engagement of industry experts underscored the commitment to driving sustainable development forward. Overall, the event served as a catalyst for further collaboration and investment opportunities, paving the way for impactful solutions to address environmental challenges.

Here is a comprehensive summary of the events that occurred throughout 2023:

- **The World Venture Forum (WVF) 2023, Kitzbühel, Austria, held from July the 3rd to 8th 2023– Greenovate! Europe, MAT, G2G, VENIONAIRE, STW.**

The 2023 edition of the World Venture Forum (WVF), hosted by Venionaire Capital, was a significant networking milestone, attracting over 500 participants from 25 countries. The event featured a mix of high-profile individuals from family offices, foundations, banks, pension funds, and well-to-do private investors. A highlight was a session led by InvestCEC partners focusing on the circular economy. During this session, discussions covered the current landscape of investments in the circular economy within Europe and internationally, highlighting the growing interest and investment in sustainable economic practices.

- **ECOMONDO – Rimini, Italy, held from 7th to 10th November at the Rimini Expo Centre – Enspire and G2G!**

In November 2023, Enspire (coordinator) G2G (business models manager) took part of ECOMONDO, an event focused on circular economy advancements, featuring sectors like waste management, bioeconomy, and water cycle, alongside innovations in textiles and ecosystem regeneration. Key highlights included discussions on sustainability, circular cities, and the launch of innovative projects aimed at ecological transition: IEG Expo), Materially and Recycling Inside. G2G presented the InvestCEC project at the CCRI-event on day 1, and visited the exhibitor stands to promote the project and invite companies to apply to the “call for entrepreneurs”. On day 2, G2G attended a pitching session from entrepreneurs and also held a stand in the EU-zone to display the project and the “call for entrepreneurs” and network with other projects.

- **1st CCRI General Conference – From vision to reality: Cities & regions drive forward Europe’s circular transition – Brussels, Belgium, held the 8th of November 2023 – Greenovate! Europe and Materialia.**

In November 2023, the European Commission hosted the inaugural CCRI conference, focusing on showcasing how cities, regions, and their partners across Europe are leveraging the wealth of energy and ideas within their territories to propel the circular economy forward and foster social innovation. This gathering provided

a platform for sharing tangible case studies, illustrating the journey from political commitment and strategic planning to the actual implementation of systemic solutions for a sustainable future.

The communications manager (Greenovate Europe) and the Replication manager (Materialia) were part of this pivotal event, not only to meet in person the CCRI community, pilots, fellows, but also network with all the other projects funded under the CCRI umbrella. This event resulted into a close collaboration to exchange practices with like-minded CCRI projects. e.g., the bioeconomy project BIOBOOST, which serves an office that

- **UN Climate Initiatives Insights – Held from the 11th to the 10th of November 2023 – Venonaire**

The event “UN Climate Initiatives Insights” focused on the visions of the United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction (UNDRR) and was attended by various experts from the industry. Attendees expressed enthusiasm for the climate initiatives discussed, emphasising the importance of shining a spotlight on such vital work. InvestCEC was one of the initiatives that were presented within the event. Overall, the event was seen as a valuable platform for exchanging ideas and promoting collaborative efforts towards a more sustainable future.

- **Austrian League of Cities – Waste Management Conference – Graz, Austria held on the 22nd of November 2023 – STW.**

At the Waste Management Conference hosted by the Austrian League of Cities. Gernot Bogensberger, head of the Waste Management Department, and Markus Scheriau, responsible for the gas segment at Stadtwerke Klagenfurt AG, showcased the "Bio-Waste-Project" and the "Bio-Gas-Project" as part of their InvestCEC presentation. The objective of their participation was to enhance inter-municipal cooperation among cities. The presentation not only detailed InvestCEC's four-stage model but also sparked significant interest from the city of Leoben. This led to the establishment of a new collaboration between Leoben and Klagenfurt, where representatives from Leoben are set to visit and explore these initiatives further, exemplifying the successful models of circular economy practices.

- **Municipal Utility Day – Vienna, Austria held on the 23rd of November 2023 – STW.**

The 11th Public Utility Day took place in Vienna in collaboration with the Association of Austrian Municipal Enterprises. The focus of the 2023 event centered on the role of public infrastructure as a catalyst for a green future. The event attracted CEOs of public utilities, various political stakeholders, and investors. The main goal was to establish a communication platform where these diverse stakeholders could converge and discuss issues related to the circular economy at the national level. A significant outcome of this gathering was the agreement between Manfred Ortner from Stadtwerke Klagenfurt AG and Heidrun Maier-de Kruijff, the managing director of the association, to include the InvestCEC in the agenda for the next Public Utility Day taking place this year.

- **Horasis India Meeting – Adelaide, Australia, held from the 26th to the 27th of November 2023 – Venonaire**

The Horasis India Meeting 2023 was set to foster impactful discussions on cooperation, impact investing, and strategies for sustainable growth. Circular Economy was a centerpiece of discussions and Berthold Baurek-

Karlic, CEO of Venionaire and a representative of InvestCEC contributed to central panel discussion focusing on “Designing for Life-Time Circularity”. The event provided an opportunity to engage in discussions with key stakeholders from the industry and has boosted the visibility and reach of InvestCEC.

- **Side Event: Planetary Health, Energy Security und KI / World Economic Forum – Venionaire**

InvestCEC stood as a sponsor and network partner alongside Venionaire at the side event “Planetary Health, Energy Security und KI” within the esteemed World Economic Forum (WEF). The event, hosted in Davos, Switzerland, served as a dynamic platform for global leaders and visionaries to exchange innovative ideas. InvestCEC vision was showcased within this forum by Venionaire itself, leading to increased visibility and overall positive impact on the project's dissemination. In addition, Venionaire as a representative of InvestCEC was an integral part of a meaningful dialogue, aligning with the core values of sustainable innovation and driving global change.

2.3. Professional articles

At the midpoint of our project, with increasing activities, professional articles are planned to be released on our website. These articles aim to showcase the milestones, best practices, and key findings of our project. This section of the website will be continually updated when InvestCEC has more to share. The first [article](#), titled 'Exploring Barriers to Circular Economy: Insights from CARTIF's Report,' provides a comprehensive analysis of the transition to a circular economy (CE). It focuses on the reuse, recycling, and regeneration of materials to minimise waste and optimise resource usage. This transition faces significant challenges, primarily financial, that must be overcome to realise CE goals. CARTIF's analysis identifies four main areas of barriers: investment-related challenges, pricing and valuation challenges, financial structures and models, and market and incentive challenges."

The second article will emerge from the preliminary replication plan of InvestCEC. This piece outlines our initial efforts to replicate the InvestCEC model and proposes a framework for adapting it within various urban and regional contexts. This article, which builds upon the initial plan, is set for subsequent phases of evaluation and refinement. These phases will consider essential feedback and insights from project partners, alongside practical knowledge gained during project implementation.

The replication plan is designed to evolve gradually as feedback is collected and integrated, with the aim of developing a practical guide that offers general recommendations for replication, sensitive to the diverse circumstances of different urban and regional environments. We aim to proceed with a cautious approach, laying a foundational framework that can inform and potentially guide similar future initiatives without overcommitting at this early stage.

2.4. Call for entrepreneurs

Another significant achievement of the InvestCEC project has been the call for entrepreneurs. As stipulated in the project's grant agreement, this "Selection process" involves both recruiting and selecting companies.

These companies are brought into the InvestCEC process by inviting them to address the needs identified in step 1, going through the selection process in step 2 and preparing them for investment readiness in step 3, and potentially considering them as candidates for the InvestCEC investment program.

The call was organised into three distinct phases:

- **Round 1:** Entrepreneurs were asked to submit a brief and straightforward online [application form](#). This method was chosen to ensure broad participation by minimising the complexity of the application process.

In the application, entrepreneurs were asked to provide concise descriptions of their products, solutions, or services, identify their target users or customers, and outline the current development stage of their offerings. Additionally, they were required to specify the resources needed to further develop their company or enhance their products, solutions, or services, such as investment, partners, or strategic advice. They also needed to explain how their offerings contribute to the principles of the circular economy.

- **Round 2:** Companies that met the specific requirement of offering a circular economy solution were selected for an initial interview conducted by G2G. These interviews were semi-structured, allowing G2G to take detailed notes that would later be used to fill out a comprehensive template based on the information provided in the application form (screenshots below).
- **Round 3:** A pitch session accompanied by a scoring late April 2024.

The participation overview for the first call for entrepreneurs was marked by an initial submission of 16 application forms. Out of these, 13 companies were selected for the second round (interviews) due to their alignment with circular economy principles, while 3 were excluded for not meeting this essential criterion. From those interviewed, 6 companies were ultimately invited to proceed to the final round of the call.

The final round of the entrepreneur selection process occurred during pitch sessions on April 25th and 26th. Each participant had a one-hour session consisting of a 5-minute pitch, a 20-minute Q&A with the panel (Venionaire, STW Klagenfurt, & Gate2Growth), followed by 30 minutes of internal scoring discussion among panel members.

The panel used scoring guidelines refined iteratively during the call process, adapting conventional startup pitch scoring to emphasise circular economy elements, particularly the level of circularity in idea and value creation and the circularity and viability of the value chain.

The top one or two scoring companies will be selected for in-depth investment readiness coaching by Gate2Growth, which includes access to online business model and budgeting tools. Venionaire will also provide valuation analysis by its team analysts.

3. Dissemination monitoring: outcomes and activities continuity

As InvestCEC reaches halfway mark in its timeline, the project is making subnational strides across several areas. It continues to actively inform and update its target group on its initiatives and remains committed to raising awareness about the benefits of the circular economy and the importance of developing green solutions suitable for EU regions or cities like Klagenfurt am Wörthersee. The project also promotes collaboration among the CCRI sister projects through thematic webinars that focus on financing a sustainable future by empowering the circular economy through effective policy, replication strategies, addressing financial barriers, and supporting entrepreneurs in achieving investment success. These efforts include actively promoting participation opportunities through various calls for engagement, ensuring extensive involvement in the project's activities. Moreover, InvestCEC is dedicated to keeping the Klagenfurt community well-informed about the project's objectives and the positive impacts it seeks to achieve. This comprehensive strategy is essential for cultivating a robust understanding and support for the circular economy within the region.

3.1. Dissemination activities

3.1.1. THEMATIC WEBINARS

As part of our continuous engagement and knowledge sharing efforts, InvestCEC has organised a series of four thematic online webinars, coordinated by Greenovate! Europe. These webinars are strategically developed to achieve the following objectives:

- **Present the initial outcomes and insights garnered from the InvestCEC initiatives.**
- **Foster dialogue and exchange perspectives with stakeholders within the circular economy and CCRI projects.**
- **Enhance the visibility and impact of the InvestCEC program.**

To effectively manage and disseminate the learnings throughout the year, the webinar series is planned to be divided into two sessions: two editions in the spring and two in the autumn of 2024.

The following topics have been identified for the webinar series:

1. **Empowering Entrepreneurs**
2. **Breaking Down Financial Barriers**
3. **Financing the Circular Future**
4. **Fostering Replication and Policy Change**

Each of these themes has been carefully chosen to reflect the core areas of focus within the InvestCEC project and to drive forward the agenda of a sustainable circular economy.

Webinar #1 Recap: Empowering Entrepreneurs for Investment Success – A Side Event of WCEF

On April 11, 2024, InvestCEC successfully hosted the first of its webinar series titled "Empowering Entrepreneurs for Investment Success," which took place virtually over Zoom and lasted for one and a half hours. The event was an important opportunity for entrepreneurs and stakeholders in the circular economy to connect and learn.

The session started with a welcome and introduction by Greenovate! Europe, setting the tone for a fruitful discussion. The agenda included:

- A presentation by Uffe Bundgaard-Jørgensen from Gate2Growth. He provided an insightful intro on the InvestCEC setup and offered strategies for navigating funding challenges in circular economy businesses. He emphasised on how entrepreneurs can overcome funding obstacles and develop comprehensive strategies to meet investor expectations.
- Tommaso Buso from Bankers without Boundaries followed with his session, which brought to light how the DEFINITE-CCRI project bolsters circular economy projects by offering specialised project development assistance to secure investment.

The webinar also featured a moment to exchange and ask questions to the speakers about the main challenges for early-stage circular economy business and how to overcome them and how start-ups could build solid and long-term financial plans that could be presented to investors. Concluding the event were the closing remarks from Greenovate! Europe, which capped off the webinar on a high note. Overall, the event was instrumental in enhancing the dialogue around investment readiness in the circular economy and provided valuable insights to all participants.

Webinar #2 Recap: Breaking Down Financial Barriers in the Circular Economy

The "Breaking Down Financial Barriers in the Circular Economy" webinar took place on April 30, 2024, from 11:00 AM to 12:30 PM CET, conducted virtually via Teams. The session was pivotal in addressing financial hurdles within the circular economy and pinpointing methods to navigate them. It also showcased DECISO's four active pilot projects, illustrating their approaches to financial obstacles in diverse settings.

Jorge Calvo Presa from CARTIF kicked off the agenda by discussing strategies for overcoming financial barriers within the circular economy. The event continued with in-depth presentations from various regions:

- Sabine Herrmann represented the City of Hamburg, sharing insights on "Strategic Framework for Financial Schemes."
- Daniel Gerdes from OOWV – Water Association of Oldenburg-Ostfriesland discussed "Optimising Rainwater Use" in North-West Germany.
- Kostas Karamarkos from the Municipal District Heating Enterprise of the Wider Area of Amyntaio (DETEPA) presented on "Decarbonisation and Post-Lignite Transition" efforts in West Macedonia.
- Rosa Onofre of CCDRA – Alentejo Regional Coordination and Development Commission explored "Circular Agri-food Business Models" in Alentejo.

The webinar concluded with an interactive session, facilitating a discussion and Q&A between the speakers and attendees, enhancing understanding and collaboration opportunities.

Continuing with the strategic dissemination plan for InvestCEC to foster dialogue and exchange perspectives with stakeholders within the circular economy and CCRI projects; InvestCEC is set to hold the third webinar of the year in autumn, focusing on "**#Financing the Circular Future.**" This aligns with the planned two webinars in the spring and another two in the autumn. The forthcoming event, targeted for November 2024, aims to connect venture capitalists, investors, policy makers, and professionals in the circular economy field through a virtual meeting. Experts will share their insights on investment strategies and engage in a panel discussion to explore collaborative opportunities, continuing the momentum of advancing circular economy initiatives.

In the final thematic webinar of InvestCEC's autumn series, "**#Empowering Circular Economy through Policy and Replication,**" set for November 2024, experts and policymakers will come together to discuss the integration of circular economy principles into regional development strategies. The session will address key policy recommendations, insights from successful replication strategies, and will foster a dialogue on how to further these practices across Europe. This webinar will be also having another sister project from the CCRI, the BIOBOOST which will contribute its expertise on bioeconomy investment strategies that can be adopted across regions.

InvestCEC will continue to ensure that resources, including content materials and project documentation, are widely available for a broad audience, cities, local and regional governments, general stakeholders, and individuals engaged in sustainable practices. Hence, to broaden outreach, for those who wish to revisit the discussions or who could not attend live the 4 thematic webinars, the InvestCEC will host recordings to facilitate widespread adoption of the project's successful strategies and synergies with other CCRI projects.

3.1.2. PLANNED ENGAGEMENT EVENTS

- **Second Circular economy day 2024 – Klagenfurt**

As part of the strategic planning for the next project meeting in autumn 2024, project partners have decided to host the meeting in Klagenfurt, Austria. This location was chosen to provide a deeper grasp of and connection with the local context. Additionally, there will be an opportunity to organise the second Circular economy day event following or before our project meeting. This event will allow us to engage with local stakeholders more effectively. Unlike previous occasions, this time we will not only be involved in preparing the event but also actively participate in it, enhancing our integration and interaction with the local community and stakeholders in Klagenfurt. The thematic focus and organisation of the event in Klagenfurt are yet to be determined.

- **Sommergespräche (summer talks) for all Austrian mayors – August 2024**

The event is a forum taking place every summer, it was created to address future municipal issues in Austria, initiated by the Austrian Association of Municipalities and Kommunalkredit. Held in Bad Aussee, it gathers national and international experts from various sectors to discuss problems, showcase best practices, and develop solutions. The event features diverse formats such as lectures, workshops, and discussions, fostering networking among participants. It has grown into a well-known knowledge platform extending beyond Austria's borders, focusing in 2023 on "Our World. Between Solidarity and Resilience." STW Klagenfurt will represent the InvestCEC project and engage in discussions with municipalities that encounter challenges similar to those faced by Klagenfurt with the aim of fostering national replication.

- **Abfallwirtschaftspreis "Phönix" April 2024**

STW Klagenfurt will participate in the Austrian Waste Management Conference 2024, scheduled for April in Vienna, with a focus on "Circular Economy Waste Management in times of change." At this event, Klagenfurt will compete for the Waste Management Award "Phoenix," having submitted several projects that highlight innovations in efficient waste sorting and active citizen participation. The main objective of attending is to engage in discussions with experts, aiming for a robust exchange of ideas and knowledge on circular economy practices. This will also be an opportunity for Klagenfurt to showcase their projects in poster sessions, targeting knowledge transfer and engagement with a specialised audience interested in sustainable waste management solutions.

- **Ecomondo – November 2024**

Ecomondo remains a pivotal event for the green and circular economy, attracting industry leaders, stakeholders, policymakers, and more to shape EU environmental strategies. This year, if invited by the European Commission again, InvestCEC will participate to engage with the circular economy ecosystem, discuss project progress, and promote its initiatives. By attending, InvestCEC reinforces its role as a leader in promoting circularity within European cities and regions.

3.2. Communication activities

3.2.1. THE INVESTCEC VIDEO

In November 2023, the InvestCEC promotional video was launched, targeting investors, regions and cities, entrepreneurs, policymakers, and the public. The aim is to engage key stakeholders who may not be aware of the project's objectives. The video was promoted on the project's website, across all partners' social media platforms, and on circular economy platforms where InvestCEC contributes content, maximising outreach.

The video details the exploration of the InvestCEC project, which is aimed at promoting the circular economy in various European locales. It begins with Berthold Baurek-Karlic from Venionaire Capital emphasising the urgent need for CO2 reduction strategies. Andrea Ratkosova from Enspire describes the project's structured approach through a four-stage model, beginning with assessing the specific needs for circular economy practices in cities and regions. Erwin Smole highlights how Klagenfurt serves as a model city, incorporating sustainability into its economic and environmental strategies, and fostering a supportive environment for startups and investors. Uffe Bundgaard-Jørgensen discusses how entrepreneurs should attract investors by presenting compelling business opportunities rather than just seeking financial aid. Joseph Hurtado extends the discussion by outlining how the project plans to replicate its success across Europe by providing guidelines that adapt to different regional contexts, promoting widespread adoption of circular economy principles. This approach aims to position Europe as a leader in circular economy investments and innovations.

3.2.2. COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES WITH THE CCRI-PDA PROJECTS

In November 2023, Greenovate! Europe organised a networking workshop aimed at fostering collaboration and enhancing communication and dissemination efforts across CCRI-PDA projects. The workshop provided a platform for participants to introduce their projects, facilitating a better understanding of each project's scope and potential synergies. Participants shared insights into their ongoing and planned communication and dissemination activities and explored initial opportunities for cross-collaboration. To support these discussions, a Miro board was utilised, enabling participants to actively input project-related information such as social media channels, target cities and regions, audience, and participation in external and project events, as well as collaboration ideas. This workshop served as a meeting point for CCRI-PDA project members to discover and develop opportunities for collaboration, ultimately aimed at increasing project visibility and outreach.

Additionally, the InvestCEC project is member of the Circular Investment Readiness Network, a collaboration initiated by CircularInvest and DEFINITE-CCRI – both CCRI-PDA projects. This network aims to advance the circular economy in Europe by helping projects secure necessary investment through guidance and Project Development Assistance. Greenovate! Europe and Enspire participated at the kick-off event and are actively involved in ongoing sessions organised by the network.

3.2.3. INVESTCEC NEWSLETTERS: GUIDING PROJECT TRAJECTORY

The InvestCEC project has successfully published three editions of its newsletter, each delivering valuable updates and insights into the project's ongoing developments. With 85 subscribers, the InvestCEC newsletter has recently expanded its presence to LinkedIn to maximise its outreach and engage a broader audience.

Newsletter Issue #1 – September 2023: this issue explores updates on our mission, including a special invitation for entrepreneurs to contribute to our circular economy initiatives. It also includes a project video introduction and highlights from our participation in significant industry events such as the Ecomondo Fair and the CCRI Conference. This newsletter serves as a gateway to staying connected with our progress and opportunities for engagement.

Newsletter Issue #2 – December 2023: The second issue continues to build on our engagement, focusing on the latest news about our project partners, the role of the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative, and our upcoming participation in ECOMONDO 2023, among other updates. This issue is designed to keep stakeholders informed about the expanding scope of our activities and the strategic directions we are pursuing.

Newsletter Issue #3 – March 2024 The third issue highlights a comprehensive recap of our latest consortium meeting in Spain and celebrates the successful conclusion of our first call for entrepreneurs. Additionally, it includes detailed information about our upcoming thematic webinars in collaboration with DEFINITE-CCRI and the DECISO project. An overview of our recent and forthcoming engagements in various events is also provided, ensuring stakeholders are well-informed of our continuous efforts and achievements.

These updates are given to provide stakeholders with insights, celebrate achievements, and outline future directions for the InvestCEC project.

3.2.4. DISCUSSION FORUM AND CASE-SPECIFIC LAB

In 2024, the InvestCEC project is pleased to announce an important update to our website's replication section. We are introducing a dedicated form where stakeholders can directly make inquiries or request specific information about replicating the InvestCEC model or any of our activities. This initiative is designed to facilitate open dialogues with those interested in adopting our approaches to advancing circular economy initiatives in their EU cities and regions. Additionally, to foster even closer ties with our stakeholders, starting from April 2024, we will initiate discussion forum on LinkedIn following our thematic webinars. We have chosen LinkedIn as our communication platform for these interactions because it provides a straightforward and effective means to engage in conversations and share insights on topics related to the circular economy. This approach is aimed at sparking enthusiasm and encouraging the exchange of knowledge among participants. This replaces the platform that was developed in WP2 (D2.2).

3.3. Marketplace and Financial Opportunities

3.3.1. SECOND CALL FOR ENTREPRENEURS

Preparations are underway for the second call for entrepreneurs within the InvestCEC project, this time with a more targeted approach that emphasises specific elements of our 4-stage model. The forthcoming call will concentrate particularly on addressing Klagenfurt's specific needs identified in the first stage and will aim to closely align with the fourth stage, which focuses on the investment fund. This strategic emphasis is intended to attract companies that can contribute to the local circular economy and are prepared for significant investment opportunities. By targeting these specific stages, the call ensures that entrepreneurs present solutions that not only meet Klagenfurt's immediate needs but are also ripe for the financial backing provided through the InvestCEC investment program, enhancing both the relevance and effectiveness of their contributions.

3.3.2. MARKETPLACE

Following our successful initial call for entrepreneurs, the InvestCEC project is currently working on its website to showcase its marketplace highlighting circular economy solutions from these innovators. This marketplace will not only increase the visibility of participating companies, but also incorporate them into a broader investment framework aimed at promoting sustainable business practices and green solutions. The layout of the marketplace will feature sufficient space for each company, including photos or videos of their solutions, descriptions of their activities, their sustainability goals, and the current status of their company or solution. This design is intended to enhance their visibility and support companies in promoting themselves to potential customers or partners.

3.3.3. FINANCIAL OPPORTUNITIES

The InvestCEC marketplace will not solely serve as a pure deal flow platform for investors. Moreover, it will act as a dynamic hub for connection and collaboration, bringing together stakeholders from across the industry to foster innovation and drive positive change. Innovative ventures will be admitted to the marketplace under the following categories as outlined in the InvestCEC fund focus: Greentech & Sustainability, Renewable Energy, Smart City Logistics, Sharing Economy, Waste Management, and Car Sharing. Potentially interested investors will gain access to a pre-selected pool of entrepreneurs, that are already within the stage Early Growth/Growth and could serve a customer the size of Stadtwerke Klagenfurt with existing products or services. This collaborative approach will not only benefit individual entrepreneurs and investors but also contribute to the broader goal of advancing sustainability and foster visibility for circular economy initiatives.

4. Conclusion and Future Directions

As the InvestCEC project progresses, it has made significant strides in embedding sustainable development and circular economy principles across European cities and regions, demonstrating practical feasibility and potential scalability through Klagenfurt's success.

Looking forward, the project aims to refine its impact by harnessing localised innovations through its second call for entrepreneurs, enhancing financial models to support these ventures, and ensuring their longevity. To maintain momentum, InvestCEC will continue working with the CCRI community and engaging stakeholders with thematic webinars and local events like the second Circular Economy Day, fostering community involvement and collaborative efforts essential for the widespread adoption and replication of circular economy practices across Europe.